

The Importance of Explainable AI for Gig Workers: A Case for Human-Centered XAI in Gig Economy

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AI-driven decision-making systems operate in the background of gig work platforms, playing a central role in job allocation, performance evaluation, and compensation. However, the opaque nature of these algorithmic systems has posed significant challenges for gig workers in terms of transparency, accountability, and fairness. Existing Explainable AI (XAI) frameworks, developed primarily for traditional domains, fail to adequately address the unique challenges and lived experiences of gig workers. This position paper argues for a tailored approach to XAI in the gig economy, building upon prior research in human-centered XAI (HCXAI). We propose future research directions aimed at developing XAI methods that center the needs and experiences of gig workers, promoting algorithmic transparency, and empowering workers in an AI-mediated labor landscape. By addressing the longstanding challenges of algorithmic opacity in gig work, we can work towards a more equitable and accountable future for this rapidly growing workforce.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The gig economy, characterized by short-term contracts and freelance work facilitated through digital platforms [2], has experienced significant growth in recent years. At the heart of this ecosystem are AI-driven decision-making systems that operate in the background, governing task allocation, performance evaluation, and compensation on platforms such as Uber, DoorDash, Amazon Mechanical Turk, UpWork, Fiverr, etc [30]. While these algorithmic systems play a crucial role in shaping the experiences of gig workers, they often function as opaque "black boxes," leaving workers with little understanding of how decisions that significantly impact their livelihoods are made [31]. This lack of transparency poses significant challenges for gig workers in terms of accountability, fairness, and the ability to contest decisions that may have far-reaching consequences, such as income instability or unfair deactivation [32]. Recent studies have documented how gig workers also experience financial and emotional challenges [33, 34]. Often, the algorithmic control creates a significant "transparency gap" between existing platform designs and the information drivers need to make informed decisions about promotions, fares, routes, and task allocation [29]. Unlike domains such as healthcare or finance, where AI users often have domain expertise and a degree of influence over the systems they interact with, gig workers are largely excluded from the development and deployment of the AI systems that govern their work [39]. This exclusion widens the power asymmetries between gig workers and platforms, further underscoring the need for Explainable AI (XAI) frameworks that cater specifically to the needs and challenges of this unique workforce.

Existing XAI research has primarily focused on developing explanations for AI systems in structured, high-stakes domains, such as medicine or law, where the intended users are often experts with domain knowledge [40, 41]. However, the dynamic, platform-mediated nature of gig work presents a distinct set of challenges that current XAI frameworks are ill-equipped to address. These challenges include asymmetrical power dynamics between workers and platforms, a lack of AI literacy among gig workers, the need for contextualized and real-time explanations in ever-changing work environments, and the pervasive algorithmic control that workers are subjected to, often without a clear understanding

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of how these systems operate [42]. Recent research has responded to these challenges through several innovative approaches. Some worker collectives have begun developing data-driven tools that crowdsource and analyze workers' data to estimate platform practices such as "take rates" – the percentage of rider prices retained by rideshare platforms [1, 37]. In one notable example, a Colorado-based rideshare union collaborated with researchers to develop FairFare, a tool that collected data on over 76,000 trips from 45 drivers over 18 months [37]. This worker-led data collection effort directly contributed to the passage of legislation requiring greater transparency and data disclosure from platforms. Additionally, researchers in CSCW and HCI communities have increasingly examined worker data collectives as a means to advance policy, hold platforms accountable for data transparency, and empower the collective worker voice [1, 29]. These efforts leverage frameworks such as data feminism to design sustainable and power-aware data collectives that address challenges in various gig sectors, including ridesharing, freelancing, crowdwork, and carework. Despite these important developments, fundamental questions remain about designing, governing, and sustaining such data infrastructures. Furthermore, design researchers have examined the impact of design decisions on who gets to design [35].

Despite these challenges, gig workers have developed a critical understanding of the algorithms that shape their work experiences through daily interactions with AI-driven platforms [36, 38]. This critical understanding highlights the gap between AI designers' intended use of algorithms and the actual lived experiences of workers. By studying how gig workers interpret and adapt to these algorithms, researchers can develop XAI frameworks that better align with their needs, provide actionable insights, and mitigate potential harms such as algorithmic bias, wage suppression, and account blocking and deactivation risks. In this position paper, we argue for a new approach to XAI that is specifically tailored to the needs and experiences of gig workers.

Building upon prior research in human-centered XAI (HCXAI) [39], we propose a research agenda aimed at developing worker-centric explanation frameworks that prioritize transparency, agency, and actionable insights. We begin by arguing the critical ways in which XAI for gig work differs from existing approaches. Next, we explore how gig workers' own critical understanding of algorithms can inform the design of explainable systems. Finally, we outline a set of research directions and questions to guide the development of XAI methods that center the needs and experiences of gig workers, ultimately contributing to a more equitable and accountable future for this rapidly growing sector of the economy.

2 WHY XAI FOR GIG WORK IS DIFFERENT

Existing XAI approaches have predominantly been developed for structured, high-stakes domains like healthcare [41] and legal contexts [40], where explanations are typically sought by domain experts. The gig economy presents fundamentally different challenges that require rethinking explanation design:

Asymmetrical Power Dynamics: Gig workers operate within a power imbalance that fundamentally shapes their interaction with algorithmic systems. Unlike professionals in healthcare or finance who typically possess institutional authority and professional standing, gig workers lack bargaining power and formal protections [3], making it difficult to contest opaque AI decisions. For example, when a gig platform like Uber, Lyft or UpWork deactivates a driver's account due to an algorithmic decision, the driver may have limited recourse to challenge the decision or seek reinstatement. Rosenblat and Stark [4] documented numerous cases where ride-hailing platforms terminated drivers based on automated systems with minimal transparency or appeal rights. Similarly, Jhaver et al. [27] found that content creators on freelance platforms frequently experienced unexplained changes in visibility or ranking with no official channels for contestation.

This power asymmetry means that explanations for gig workers cannot simply focus on technical transparency but must explicitly address questions of worker agency and contestability.

Lack of AI Literacy: The gig economy includes workers with widely varying levels of education, technical expertise, and familiarity with algorithmic systems [26, 31]. Many workers do not have technical backgrounds, necessitating explanations that are both interpretable and actionable without requiring specialized knowledge.

For example, a freelance writer on Upwork may find it challenging to comprehend how the platform's algorithm determines their job recommendations or search rankings, limiting their ability to optimize their profile and secure more clients. Prior work found significant variations in AI literacy among platform workers, with many struggling to interpret even basic algorithmic concepts [7, 32]. This heterogeneity in technical literacy makes conventional XAI approaches ineffective, as they typically assume a baseline level of technical understanding that varies widely among gig workers across different platforms.

Dynamic Work Environments: Unlike traditional workplaces with relatively stable conditions, gig work involves ever-changing environments requiring contextualized and real-time explanations [42]. The algorithmic systems governing gig work frequently adapt to changing market conditions, economic and geographic factors, and temporal patterns, creating a constantly shifting landscape for workers [25, 30].

A freelance graphic designer on a gig platform must navigate a constantly shifting landscape of client preferences, market trends, and platform policies, making it difficult to rely on static explanations of the algorithms that govern their work. Wood et al. [30] documented how platform algorithms may change behavior based on localized supply and demand, time of day, or even individual worker history. These dynamic conditions mean explanations must be contextual and adaptive rather than universal and static.

The temporal urgency of gig work creates additional challenges for explanation design. Food delivery workers often have only seconds to decide whether to accept an assignment [23], making lengthy or complex explanations impractical. This urgency requires explanation approaches that can deliver critical information efficiently within the workflow constraints of gig work.

Algorithmic Control: Gig platforms deploy sophisticated control mechanisms that extend beyond simple task allocation to shape worker behavior through incentives, constraints, and surveillance [4, 30]. Workers are subjected to algorithmic nudging, gamification, and monitoring, often without understanding how these systems operate or their cumulative effects.

For instance, a worker on a microtask platform like Amazon Mechanical Turk may be pressured to accept lower-paying tasks or work longer hours due to the platform's reputation system and task allocation algorithms. Prior work [14] documented how these control mechanisms create a form of "digital piecework" where workers must continuously optimize their behavior to algorithmic requirements without fully understanding those requirements.

These control mechanisms can have significant consequences for worker wellbeing and autonomy. Prior work [13, 34] found that opaque performance metrics create anxiety and uncertainty among ride-hailing drivers, who develop elaborate theories and workarounds to navigate algorithmic evaluation systems. Explanations in this context must go beyond individual decisions to illuminate broader patterns of algorithmic management and their effects on worker agency.

These four dimensions demonstrate why conventional XAI approaches are insufficient for gig work contexts. An effective framework must simultaneously address power asymmetries, diverse technical backgrounds, dynamic work environments, and pervasive control mechanisms. This requires moving beyond technical transparency to consider

worker agency, contextual explanations, and collective understanding. The following sections build on these insights to propose a worker-centered XAI framework that addresses these unique challenges.

3 CRITICAL ALGORITHMS AND GIG WORKERS' UNDERSTANDING

Gig workers have developed a critical understanding of the algorithms that shape their work experiences through their daily interactions with AI-driven platforms. Despite the opacity of these systems, workers have learned to recognize patterns in task distribution, payment fluctuations, and ranking systems [31, 38]. This process of algorithmic sensemaking occurs through both individual experience and collective knowledge sharing. Workers actively experiment with platform systems to identify how algorithmic decisions affect their earnings and opportunities. Rosenblat [10] documented how ride-hailing drivers develop detailed mental models of surge pricing patterns by systematically testing different locations and times. Similarly, Wood et al. [30] found that food delivery workers identify temporal patterns in order allocation to maximize their earnings throughout the day. Many workers extend this learning process beyond individual discovery by sharing knowledge through online forums, social media groups, and messaging platforms [36]. These communities collectively decode the "black box" mechanisms that govern their livelihoods. Recent work [9, 11] observed how freelancers on global platforms share techniques for optimizing profile visibility and securing better assignments through keyword strategies and profile adjustments. This critical understanding is significant for Explainable AI because it highlights the gap between AI designers' intended use of algorithms and the actual lived experiences of workers. By studying how gig workers interpret and adapt to these algorithms, researchers can develop XAI frameworks that better align with their practical needs. Rather than generic explanations of algorithmic principles, AI systems should provide actionable insights that allow workers to strategize and optimize their performance while ensuring fair treatment. Workers' existing knowledge reveals what aspects of algorithmic systems they find most consequential. Prior work [15, 22] found that workers often prioritize understanding earnings calculations and assignment systems over other algorithmic functions. This suggests that explanation systems should focus on these high-impact areas rather than technical details that may be less relevant to worker concerns. Furthermore, an explainability framework tailored to gig workers can mitigate potential harms such as algorithmic bias, wage suppression, and account deactivation risks. Research has documented how the opacity of platform algorithms can enable discriminatory practices [16, 28] and gradual reduction of worker compensation [31]. Transparent explanations could help workers identify and contest such practices. Ensuring that workers understand the rationale behind AI decisions is crucial for fostering trust and enabling meaningful contestability. As prior work on XAI [17, 20] suggest, explanations must support not just understanding but also actionable recourse—clear paths for workers to address problems or challenge unfair decisions. Therefore, Explainable AI for gig workers is not merely about technical transparency but about empowering a workforce that heavily depends on AI-driven platforms for economic survival. An effective approach to XAI for gig workers must recognize and build upon workers' existing algorithmic knowledge. This requires a participatory approach to explanation design that includes workers as stakeholders rather than merely end-users. In the following section, we outline a research agenda for developing such worker-centered explanation frameworks.

4 A CALL FOR A NEW STUDY ON XAI FOR GIG WORK

We propose a dedicated research agenda for Gig Work XAI:

- (1) **Developing explanations that prioritize worker agency and understanding** requires moving beyond technical transparency to focus on actionable insights. Drawing from participatory and co design approaches

[18, 19, 21], these frameworks should incorporate worker perspectives from the outset rather than retrofitting explanations to worker needs. This includes investigating what types of decisions workers most need explanations for (e.g., task allocation, pricing, performance evaluation), what level of detail is most useful in different contexts, and how explanations can support not just understanding but also contestation of unfair algorithmic decisions. For example, a worker-centric explanation framework might provide ride-hailing drivers with specific insights about how acceptance rates affect future ride assignments, including concrete actions they can take to improve their position.

- (2) **AI Literacy Interventions:** Studying how different explanation styles impact gig workers' trust, understanding, and autonomy is essential for developing effective XAI systems. This research direction examines how explanations can accommodate varying levels of technical literacy without creating additional barriers to participation in platform work. Potential approaches include progressive disclosure models that provide basic explanations initially with options to access more detailed information, visual explanations that reduce reliance on technical terminology, and peer-learning approaches that leverage workers' existing knowledge-sharing practices [38]. These interventions should be evaluated not just on comprehension metrics but on how they affect workers' ability to make informed decisions about their work.
- (3) **Power-Aware XAI:** Integrating feminist and intersectional approaches to address systemic inequities in AI-driven gig work represents a critical departure from conventional XAI frameworks [42]. This research direction examines how explanation design can acknowledge and potentially rebalance power asymmetries between workers and platforms. This includes investigating how collective explanations could support various groups of workers, and how explanation frameworks might be designed to support regulatory oversight and policy interventions. Power-aware XAI recognizes that explanation is not neutral but can either reinforce or challenge existing power structures in the platform economy.
- (4) **Real-Time, Contextual Explanations:** Ensuring that explanations adapt to gig workers' tasks and environments addresses the dynamic nature of platform work [31, 36, 40]. This research direction explores how explanations can be delivered in ways that align with workers' workflows and decision-making processes. Key questions include how to provide timely explanations for time-sensitive decisions (e.g., whether to accept a ride request), how explanations might adapt to different contexts (e.g., high vs. low demand periods), and how to balance the need for immediate information with more comprehensive understanding. This may involve developing new interaction models for delivering explanations within existing platform interfaces or creating complementary tools that workers can consult during their work.

To advance this research agenda, we propose the following research questions:

- How do gig workers currently interpret and navigate algorithmic decision-making? What mental models do they develop through experience, and how do these models influence their work strategies and decisions?
- What kinds of explanations do gig workers find most useful and actionable? How do factors such as timing, format, level of detail, and actionability affect the utility of explanations in different work contexts?
- How do power dynamics influence the effectiveness of AI explanations for gig workers? How might explanations address or potentially reinforce existing power imbalances between workers and platforms?
- What role does AI literacy play in improving the usability and impact of XAI systems for gig workers? How can explanations accommodate varying levels of technical understanding without creating additional barriers to participation?

Understanding these questions is crucial to developing an XAI framework that aligns with gig workers' needs. A well-designed XAI system can empower gig workers by providing clarity on how AI decisions are made, enabling them to make informed choices, challenge unfair decisions, and optimize their work strategies. Furthermore, ensuring that XAI accounts for power asymmetries and social contexts is essential to fostering equitable working conditions in AI-driven labor markets.

5 CONCLUSION

The gig economy presents unique challenges that demand a rethinking of XAI frameworks. In this position paper, we argued why the existing approaches to explainability fail to address the specific needs of gig workers, who face asymmetrical power dynamics, lack of AI literacy, dynamic work environments, and pervasive algorithmic control. These distinctive characteristics of platform-mediated labor require explanation approaches that go beyond technical transparency. Gig workers have already developed sophisticated understandings of the algorithms that govern their work through daily interactions and collective knowledge sharing. By building on this existing knowledge and prior HCXAI research, we advocate for a worker-centered research agenda that prioritizes explanations that are contextual, actionable, and power-aware. As platform-based work continues to expand globally, worker-centered XAI approaches will only grow in importance. By empowering gig workers with meaningful explanations of the systems that govern their livelihoods, we can work toward a more equitable and accountable future for AI-driven labor markets.

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